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Review Paper

Appraising trapping efficiency of vegetative barriers in agricultural landscapes: Strategy based on a probabilistic approach based on a review of available information

José-Antonio Muñoz ^{a,*}, Gema Guzmán ^{a,b}, María-Auxiliadora Soriano ^c, José A. Gómez ^a

^a Institute for Sustainable Agriculture (IAS)-CSIC, Cordoba, 14004, Spain

^b Andalusian Institute of Agricultural and Fisheries Research and Training (IFAPA), Granada, 18004, Spain

^c Agronomy Department (DAUCO), University of Cordoba, Cordoba, 14071, Spain

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ABSTRACT

Vegetative barriers have proven their effectiveness in controlling water erosion and enhancing other ecosystem services in agricultural areas. This characteristic has led to the conservation and promotion of vegetative barriers as landscape elements by the Common Agricultural Policy and other policy initiatives. Numerous reviews have dealt with the trapping efficiency of vegetated barriers, although they usually focus on studies from humid climates where their implantation and survival are more favourable. However, vegetated barriers are also an attractive alternative in arid and semi-arid climates. They limit competition for water and nutrients with crops to a reduced area compared to other best management practices, such as cover crops. This study presents a review of trapping efficiency of sediment, runoff, and nutrients (P and N) by vegetative barriers in regions of humid and arid, and semi-arid, climates, and a strategy based on sediment trapping efficiency probability, which in turn is based on the results obtained from our review. Different types of independent variables were grouped and identified for the review: related to the vegetative barrier dimension (buffer width, slope of the plot, and buffer area ratio), and related to the experimental conditions (type of vegetation in the buffer, soil protection of the non-buffered area, type of climate, type of experimental measurement and origin of rainfall). An exploratory analysis evaluated the significance of the experimental variables, which identified the need to focus on experiments under natural rainfall since those carried out with simulated rainfall presented statistically significant differences. In general, average trapping efficiencies for runoff and sediment were 40.1 and 62.6 %, respectively. For nutrients, values of trapping efficiencies had an average of 44.9 % for phosphorus and 38.4 % for nitrogen. Runoff and sediment trapping efficiency in arid and semi-arid regions tended to be higher than in humid regions. Regarding dimensional variables, a positive trend was observed in the runoff and sediment trapping efficiency with the width of the vegetative barrier, with a large variability across all the width range. Finally, based on the results of our review, we developed a probabilistic model for sediment trapping efficiency as a normalised cumulative probability distribution function for the two climatic regions separately. Also, we developed it as a function of the width of the vegetative barrier for each climatic region, to facilitate decision-making. This model shows that in 92 % of the cases, a vegetative barrier will reduce erosion in humid climates, while this trapping efficiency will be 100 % in semi-arid and arid conditions. This analysis showed that vegetative barriers are an alternative to other best management practices, e.g. cover crops, when there are operational or agronomic impediments to their implementation, having a high success rate in reducing erosion in any agricultural area.

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* Corresponding author.

E-mail address: ja.munoz@ias.csic.es (J.-A. Muñoz).

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1. Introduction

Vegetative barriers may be defined as permanent strips of dense vegetation (e.g. hedgerows, grass strips) located across concentrated flow areas or along the contour of slopes (Natural Resources Conservation Service [NRCS], 2010). One of their main purposes is the trapping of sediment, runoff and/or nutrients (Doriz et al., 2006; Wolka et al., 2018) reducing the hydrologic connectivity across the landscape. This vegetation may have, additionally, many other secondary functions such as promoting biodiversity, pest control, wind erosion reduction, enhancement of pollination, biomass production, etc. (Dufková, 2007; Christen & Dalgaard, 2013; Pätzold et al., 2007; Unger et al., 2013). Therefore, vegetative barriers are a multifunctional management practice to improve ecosystem services (ES) which should be promoted in agricultural landscapes (Haddaway et al., 2018). They are found mainly on the edge of agricultural fields, forming part in some cases of riparian zones or being the dividing line between farms.

Other vegetation best management practises, like cover crops, have demonstrated to be highly effective in reducing runoff and sediment losses in semi-arid agricultural areas (e.g. Burguet et al., 2018). However, the implementation of cover crops in water limited environments remains a challenge, mainly for the risk of competition for soil water with the main crop (Gómez, 2017; Winter et al., 2018; Soriano et al., 2023). To minimize this risk in water-limited environments, like Mediterranean areas, a strategy pursued is the use of temporary cover crops, killing the vegetation at the onset of the dry season (Gómez, 2017; Gómez and Soriano, 2020). The need for balancing cover crop growth vs. competition for soil water results in many cases in poor ground cover by the cover crops and so limited provision of ES (Guzmán et al., 2019), or increased costs as compared to bare soil management (Schütte et al., 2020). Because of these issues, it is apparent that there is the need to explore alternatives for implementing cover crops in water-limited environments, but also that it will be situations, like

in arid areas, where they will not be feasible to be implemented. In this context, in agricultural landscapes in water-limited environments, vegetative barriers might provide a viable alternative to the use of vegetation for erosion control and the provision of other ES. The spontaneous vegetation in semi-arid zones is usually conditioned by the landform, generating vegetation patterns in bands where water flow or diffusion processes are dominant, often with stripes of vegetation along drainage lines (Saco & Moreno-de las Heras, 2013), showing a major irregular distribution of the vegetation. By concentrating the use of vegetation in a smaller part of the landscape where runoff is concentrated, vegetative barriers, as compared to cover crops, can minimize the risk of competition for water with the main crop while, if properly implemented, they can be highly efficient in the provision of ES. Even so, we still find differences in the development of this strategy. In humid climates with less water limitation, the vegetative barriers usually have a dense mixture of herbaceous species, creating strips of vegetation within the crop (Schulte et al., 2017). In drier climates, this strategy of a dense herbaceous barrier is less common or more difficult to achieve. Herbaceous vegetation may not develop properly, so woody vegetation is predominant, creating hedgerows in non-cultivated areas with shallower soils and/or field boundaries (Mora et al., 2019).

Through the intensive use of vegetation, vegetative barriers create a permanent obstacle to runoff that allows the reduction of its velocity, favouring infiltration and sedimentation. In this way, they create a disruption in sediment connectivity, described as the degree of ease that a basin transfers sediment from a source through itself (Heckmann et al., 2018) reaching the outlet of the basin in many cases. Additionally, creating a permanent vegetated structure in water-limited environments, unlike temporary cover crops, can enhance the positive effects of vegetation on the provision of ES (Hall et al., 2020). In fact, a review of current agricultural policy plans shows an increasing interest in promoting vegetative barriers for different purposes. For instance, Canada and the USA

already have measures that encourage buffer zones in some of their jurisdictions (Gene et al., 2019). In the European Union (EU), the incoming period of the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP), 2023–2027, will promote the use of ecological focus areas “EFAs” (Nilsson et al., 2019), with the establishment of vegetative barriers being one of the main EFAs promoted.

For proper dissemination of the use of vegetative barriers in agricultural landscapes, it is necessary to have detailed information on their effectiveness under different conditions. Although there is significant knowledge about the use of these barriers, it tends to come mainly from humid climates (Anderson et al., 2020; Liu et al., 2012; Wanyama et al., 2012). In general, studies on vegetative barriers in humid climates have found a correlation between sediment trapping and variables related to their dimension, like the width of the barrier or the slope of the terrain. Liu et al. (2008) observed that increasing the buffer width increased the sediment trapping efficiency, as expected, with a logarithmic trend, while the highest trapping values occurred with a slope between 8 and 10 %, following a quadratic relationship. Also, Yuan et al. (2009) grouped the trapping efficiencies according to the slope of the plot, reporting higher sediment trapping efficiency on slopes less than 5 % than on slopes steeper than 5 %, maintaining the logarithmic relationship with the buffer width.

Phosphorus and nitrogen are the nutrients with enough data to observe the effectiveness of vegetative barriers on their transport and trapping (e.g. Cole et al., 2020; Hoffmann et al., 2009), obtaining similar results to those observed for sediment. Nevertheless, there was also a large unexplained variability among the different studies. For instance, Helmers et al. (2005) established a 13-m width buffer filter that trapped 80 % of the sediment income, while Yang et al. (2015) managed to trap 90 % of the sediment with a barrier of 3-m width. In other cases, it has been reported some vegetative barriers have shown higher soil losses as compared to the control with bare soil (Gilley et al., 2000; Hay et al., 2006; Liu et al., 2012).

However, to the best of our knowledge, there is a very low number of studies evaluating the efficiency of vegetative barriers in arid and semi-arid environments. One of the few studies is that of Kiepe (1996), located in semi-arid zone of Kenya, which was carried out with vegetative barriers 0.5 m wide and with a slope of 14 %, obtaining efficiencies in sediment trapping of 95 %. However, with this same width and less slope (9 %), Salah et al. (2016) obtained average efficiencies of 67 % in the semi-arid zone of Palestine. There is, overall, a greater uncertainty about the trapping efficiencies of vegetative barriers in arid and semi-arid regions as compared to humid areas.

A way to extrapolate the results of the experimental studies is the use of simulation models (e.g. Merritt et al., 2003). There are several models used to evaluate and predict the efficiency in runoff and sediment trapping of vegetative barriers. Among them is VFSSMOD (Muñoz-Carpena et al., 1999), a process-based model designed to study the hydrology and sediment transport through filter strips at hillslope scale. There are other modelling approaches based on more empirical descriptions of the processes determining the efficiency of vegetative barriers, like USLE (Rodríguez, 1997) or WaTEM/SEDEM (Batista et al., 2022). A hybrid approach is that of Mahoney et al. (2018), whom developed a watershed scale model to predict the modification of hydrological connectivity, using a probability function for the efficiency of the vegetative barriers. This probabilistic approach might have a large potential for incorporating the variability in the efficiency of vegetative barriers in the models analysis at different scales (Tziliivakis et al., 2019). These modelling approaches will benefit from a better understanding of the sources of variability in experimental studies on the efficiency of vegetative barriers.

Fig. 1. Flow diagram showing the search and refinement of articles, variables and analysis through the systematic process. Climate types: humid, HU, and semi-arid or arid, SA-A.

The final goal of this study was to provide an appraisal of the effectiveness of vegetative barriers in agricultural landscapes in trapping runoff, sediment, and nutrients in overland flow, based on already published studies. The specific objectives were:

- 1 Carry out an in-depth review of published studies on the efficiency of vegetative barriers in reducing runoff, sediment and nutrients in overland flow across different types of climate.

- 2 Analyse the variability of the efficiency in trapping runoff, sediment and nutrients by vegetative barriers due to environmental conditions and design characteristics of the experiment.
- 3 Explore the possibility of developing a probabilistic model between trapping efficiencies and vegetative barrier dimension variables, with the aim of its incorporation into different modelling approaches.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Literature search and filter criteria

A literature search was conducted using the Web of Science bibliographic database, combining different search criteria. The first one was a general search, finished on October 18, 2021, using as search terms “review* buffer strip*” (Topic) OR “review* filter strip*” (Topic) OR “review* vegetative barrier*” (Topic) (Table S1). The available experimental base of most of the several reviews on the subject still limited. This is so because many of them are based, in a large extend, on the same articles carried out, most of them on humid climates in the Northern Hemisphere. These suggest the need of additional reviews on the subject encompassing wider environmental conditions. Due to this, our review was complemented by further additional searches for arid and semi-arid areas, completed on December 15, 2021 (Table S1), and a last search for countries of the Mediterranean basin (Table S1), completed at the same date. Fig. 1 depicts the search process undertaken.

The papers were screened, first based on their title and abstract, and then selected papers were read to identify those containing quantitative data on runoff, sediment and nutrients transport in overland flow to vegetative barriers. Our review found a very limited number of experimental studies related to nutrient losses, and these focused on phosphorus and nitrogen (Table S2). Three kind of papers were excluded from our final selection: 1- laboratory experimental plots; 2- papers presenting only concentration data; 3- those where the plot with the vegetative barrier had a ratio between the contributing area and the buffer area ≤ 1 since they represent not vegetative barriers but cover crops, except for direct runoff simulations (Abu-Zreig et al., 2004) where sediment flow conditions are known and applied directly to the vegetative barrier.

After this literature search, from an initial sample of 707 experimental plots (637 in humid areas and 70 in semi-arid and arid areas), we ended up with 56 papers (44 in humid areas and 12 in semi-arid and arid areas) that were used in our quantitative analysis.

2.2. Variables for quantitative analysis

The experimental data from these studies were grouped for analysis according to the different variables of interest. The dependent variables include the trapping efficiencies of the vegetative barrier. The efficiencies of vegetative barriers analysed were: the trapping efficiency of i) runoff, ii) sediment, and iii) phosphorus and nitrogen. In the case of nutrients, the total loads were analysed, not delving into fractional loads (i.e., soluble reactive phosphorus). On the other hand, the independent variables were grouped into two subsets: dimension variables and experimental variables. The vegetative barrier dimension variables analysed were: i) the width of the barrier, ii) the slope of the plot, and iii) the ratio between the area or length of the buffer zone and the area or length of the complete plot. The experimental variables for data analysis were: i) the type of vegetation in the buffer zone (herbaceous strip “HS”, and woody or herbaceous-woody combination strip as a mix strip

“MS”; ii) the soil protection of the non-buffered area (bare soil “BS” or some type of cover “NBS”); iii) the type of climate (humid “HU” or semi-arid and arid “SA–A”); iv) the type of experimental measurement (see below), and v) the origin of the rainfall (natural or simulated).

The trapping efficiency was calculated from the data available in the mass tests of the particles displaced outside the plot according to Eq. (1):

$$T_E = 100 \cdot \frac{M_c - M_b}{M_c} \quad (1)$$

where T_E is the trapping efficiency (%); M_c is the mass, or volume in the case of runoff, of material loss at the end of the control plot (kg or L), and M_b is the material loss at the end of the plot with vegetative barrier (kg or L). In those papers where these data are not included, we take the trapping efficiency available in percent exposed for the own authors.

Regarding the vegetation type, two main types were considered: 1- Herbaceous strip (HS), including only herbaceous vegetation, and 2- Mix strip (MS), including any type of woody species (trees and/or shrubs), but can also include herbaceous species. In the MS type, three types of vegetation strips were differentiated for exploratory analyses: only woody, shrubs or trees, strip (WS); herbaceous-woody interleaved in the same strip (HWS), and blocks strip (BLS), where the vegetative barrier is specifically designed with differentiated herbaceous, shrubs or tree strips (Schmitt et al., 1999). Although many studies have divided vegetated strips into homogeneous and heterogeneous vegetation categories (e.g. Gumiere et al., 2011), we considered this classification more operational and informative.

For the condition of the non-buffer area, we have differentiated between cases where the upstream plot area was fallow with a bare soil, or where there was some type of soil protection, like crops or mulching.

For the climate, we have compared between humid and semi-arid or arid regions, according to the Köppen–Geiger climate classification (e.g. Peel et al., 2007). In our review, semi-arid and arid climates encompass all those included in group B (arid climates) and in subgroups Cs and Cw (temperate climates, C, with dry summer and dry winter, respectively). Humid climates encompass those included in group A (tropical climates) and in subgroups Cf and Df (temperate, C, and cold, D, climates without a dry season). Experimental plots located in polar (E) or cold climates with a dry season (Ds and Dw) were discarded from the review.

The type of experimental measure was the two different ways to determinate the trapping effectiveness of a vegetative barrier: 1-

Table 1

Analysis of the impact on the different trapping efficiencies of the different experimental variables, according to the Kruskal-Wallis H-test for all the experimental data set. Results in bold indicate significant differences at $p < 0.05$ (n = data number). *Comparison between herbaceous and mix vegetation strips (HS vs. MS); **Comparison among herbaceous (HS), woody (WS), herbaceous and woody combination (HWS) and blocks (BLS) strips; ***Comparison between humid vs. semi-arid or arid regions.

p value (experimental variable)	Trapping efficiency			
	Runoff	Sediment	Phosphorus	Nitrogen
p (vegetation type, 2)*	0.5441	0.9360	0.2641	0.5350
p (vegetation type, 4)**	0.0060	0.2390	0.0010	0.0578
p (condition of non-buffer)	0.2283	0.0283	0.0001	0.0029
p (climate type)***	0.0027	0.8917	0.5125	0.0228
p (type of measure)	0.0029	0.0025	0.3777	0.0021
p (rainfall type)	0.0016	0.0009	0.0001	0.0003
n	533	661	210	147

Comparing a plot with a vegetative barrier with a bare control plot, which is the most common way, and 2- Other types of measures within the vegetative barriers. For instance, Helmers et al. (2005) installed three samplers on the upstream edge and another three samplers downstream of the vegetative barrier to measure the inflows and outflows of water and sediment.

The criteria of the rain were natural or simulated weather conditions with known rainfall intensity and duration. Also, runoff simulation with no rainfall was included in the simulated conditions (rainfall-runoff simulation).

2.3. Determination of significant experimental variables

In a first exploratory analysis, we evaluated the significance of the experimental variables described in section 2.2.: vegetation type in the buffer zone (two types: herbaceous strip, HS, and mix strip, MS; or four types: herbaceous strip, HS, woody strip, WS, herbaceous-woody combination strip, HWS, and blocks strip, BLS); conditions of the non-buffer area; type of climate; type of experimental measure, and origin of the rainfall (natural or simulated).

For each experimental variable, trapping efficiency data were analysed with the non-parametric Kruskal-Wallis H test, which ascertains whether there are statistically significant differences between two or more types of an independent experimental variable. The test determines whether the medians of two or more types of the independent variable are different or not.

Our review focuses on field conditions and avoiding dependency between the mentioned experimental variables, if possible. After the initial analysis, we determined if it was necessary to eliminate any type of an experimental variable to analyse only situations more representative of natural field conditions.

2.4. Probability distribution function of sediment trapping efficiency

An alternative or complementary approach to a mechanistic description of the differences in the sediment trapping efficiency of vegetative barriers, based on variables like buffer width, vegetation type, plot slope, buffer area ratio, etc., tried in previous reviews, e.g. Gumiere et al., 2011 (see Table S3), can be a probabilistic approach.

Table 2

Analysis of the impact on the different trapping efficiencies of the different experimental variables, according to the Kruskal-Wallis H-test with data from natural rainfall and paired plots (bare control vs. vegetative barrier). Results in bold indicate significant differences at $p < 0.05$ ($n =$ data number). *Comparison between the herbaceous and mix vegetation strips (HS vs. MS); **Comparison among herbaceous (HS), woody (WS) and herbaceous and woody combination (HWS) strips; block strips (BLS) were discarded for limited number of replications; ***Comparison between humid vs. semi-arid or arid regions.

p value (experimental variable)	Trapping efficiency			
	Runoff	Sediment	Phosphorus	Nitrogen
p (vegetation type, 2)*	0.1705	0.0235	0.0493	0.8956
p (vegetation type, 3)**	0.0009	0.0683	0.0029	NA
p (condition of non-buffer)	0.0012	0.4308	0.2694	0.5187
p (climate type)***	0.0001	0.0001	NA	NA
n	168	167	74	48

To do this, the average normalised sediment trapping efficiency was calculated from the reviewed studies, to determine the normalised cumulative probability distribution function. The cumulative probability distribution function of the normalised sediment trapping efficiency indicates the probability that a given vegetative barrier takes a value lower than or equal to a known value of sediment trapping efficiency.

After this, we deepened the possibility of a probability distribution function according to most dimension and experimental variables. We classified the vegetative barrier dimension variables into different ranges to provide an estimate of the expected trapping efficiency. Specifically, the width of the vegetative barrier was our central dimension variable, the most studied variable in previous reviews (see Table S4), and climate was our main experimental variable, one of our paper purposes. Due to this, we studied the differences in sediment trapping efficiency between humid, and arid and semi-arid climates, with vegetative barriers of different width ranges.

3. Results

3.1. Determination of significant experimental variables

Table 1 displays the significance of the different experimental

Fig. 2. Geographical distribution of experimental plots included in the review. The size of the points represents the number of experimental plots in each area. The colour of the point represents its status: discarded because it comes from simulated rainfall and types to measure trapping efficiency other than paired plots which showed significant differences (yellow), situated in humid regions (blue), or situated in arid or semi-arid region (red).

variables on the trapping efficiencies of the vegetative barrier measured (runoff, sediment and nutrients), using the complete dataset. Runoff trapping efficiency was significantly correlated ($p < 0.05$) with most of the experimental variables, except for the condition of the non-buffer area and the vegetation type when it

refers to the two main types (HS vs. MS). Regarding sediment-trapping efficiency, the measurement methodology, the condition of the non-buffer area and the origin of the rainfall were the experimental variables that significantly affected it. In the case of phosphorus trapping efficiency, there were significant correlations

Fig. 3. Relationship between runoff trapping efficiency (%) and: (a) vegetative buffer width (m); (b) buffer area ratio (vegetative buffer area/plot area; dimensionless), and (c) slope of the plot (%). All by two climate types: humid, HU, and semi-arid or arid, SA-A. Number of data points: a) 115 HU, 50 SA-A; b) 87 HU, 46 SA-A, and c) 111 HU, 47 SA-A.

with the type of vegetation, when it was classified into four types, and with the condition of the non-buffer area and the type of rainfall. Nitrogen trapping efficiency was significantly correlated with the type of measurement used, the condition of the non-buffer area, the type of rainfall and the type of climate.

The origin of the rainfall (natural or simulated) used in the experimental plots was the variable that showed a significant effect on the four trapping efficiencies evaluated (runoff, sediment, phosphorus and nitrogen). For this reason, further analysis was made on experiments coming from natural rainfall. Regarding the type of experimental measurement, it showed a significant effect on most of the trapping efficiencies evaluated (the only exception was for phosphorus). For this reason, further analysis used only the experiments that compared experimental plots with a vegetative barrier with a control-bare soil plot. This was done to analyse only situations that are more representative of natural conditions, limiting bias in our analysis.

After this, we performed a second exploratory analysis using only results coming from experiments with natural rainfall and only from paired plots (bare control vs. vegetated barrier). This subset comprises 189 experimental plots (136 in humid areas and 53 in semi-arid or arid areas), reported in 29 papers (21 in humid areas and 8 in semi-arid or arid areas), (Table S2). Fig. 2 displays a world map with the approximate location of the field experiments, differentiating between those excluded by statistical testing, and those situated in humid, and arid and semi-arid regions. The results of this analysis, with data from experiments closer to natural conditions, shown in Table 2. Datasets with insufficient data to perform a Kruskal-Wallis H test were discarded; these were BLS vegetation type in all trapping efficiencies, HWS vegetation type in nitrogen trapping efficiency, and climate in nutrients trapping efficiency.

Results in Table 2 show that runoff trapping efficiency was significantly affected by the type of vegetation (when it was classified into three types), as well as by the condition of the non-buffer area and the type of climate. Sediment trapping efficiency was affected by the vegetation type in the vegetative barrier (classified into two types), and by the type of climate. In the case of nutrients (phosphorus and nitrogen), a significant effect was only detected between the type of vegetation in the vegetative barrier (two and three types) and the efficiency of phosphorus trapping.

Due to the many variables involved, and to clarify their analysis, each of the following subsections addresses separately the different efficiencies (runoff, sediment, and nutrients) analysed in vegetative barriers. Within each subsection the effect of the different experimental variables (overall results, type of climate, type of vegetation in the buffer zone, and soil protection in the non-buffered area) are described and discussed.

3.2. Runoff trapping efficiency

Runoff trapping efficiency for the whole dataset evaluated averaged 40.1 %, with a range of –81.0 to 99.9 % (see Table S3 for all trapping-efficiency values). It is worth noting that six studies reported negative values of runoff reduction; that is, higher runoff values were measured in the plots with a vegetative barrier than in the bare plots.

Runoff trapping efficiency in arid and semi-arid regions tended to be higher than in humid regions (Kruskal-Wallis H test, $p = 0.0001$; Table 2 and S3; Fig. 3), with average values of 62.9 vs. 29.6 % (median value of 66 vs. 33 %), and ranging from –24 to 98 % vs. –81.0 to –99.9 % for arid and semi-arid vs. humid regions, respectively. Fig. 3(a) shows the runoff reduction by the vegetative barrier vs. bare soil according to the barrier width, distinguishing between humid or arid and semi-arid climatic conditions. There

was an overall trend towards higher runoff trapping efficiency with increasing width of the vegetative barrier, albeit with a large variability within each width. It is also apparent the smaller width of the vegetative barrier used in the experiments carried out in arid or semi-arid climate (generally lower than 4-m). Experiments in arid and semi-arid regions have been carried out in plots tending to have a higher vegetative barrier area ratio (i.e., area covered by the barrier/total plot area), which is usually above 0.5 (Fig. 3(b)). Simultaneously, experiments in arid and semi-arid regions tended to be conducted on steeper plots than in humid regions (Fig. 3(c)). In fact, many of the experiments in arid and semi-arid regions are carried out on slopes steeper than 20 %, resulting in a great variability in trapping efficiency values (Francia-Martínez et al., 2006; Martínez-Raya et al., 2006; Durán et al., 2008).

Fig. 4 explores the effect of vegetation type (herbaceous strip, HS; woody strip, WS; herbaceous-woody combination strip, HWS, and blocks strip, BLS) on runoff trapping efficiency, according to the dimension variables (buffer width, buffer area ratio, and plot slope). Fig. 4 does not differentiate by type of climate due to the limited number of studies available for some vegetation types. A first feature to note is that only the experiments using an HS barrier cover the whole range of widths, area ratios and slopes, except for very steep slopes (Fig. 4(a), (b), (c)), which should be considered when interpreting the effect of vegetation type.

HS barriers presented an average runoff trapping efficiency of 36.7 %, slightly lower than that measured in MS (45.5 % on average). For the different strip types including woody species, the average runoff efficiency was 53.8 and 20.7 % for WS and HWS, respectively, with statistically significant differences (Table 2), showing a large variability within each vegetation type for any buffer width, buffer area ratio or plot slope (Fig. 4). WS barriers showed a wide distribution of buffer area ratio and plot slope values, but most were very narrow in buffer width (>3-m only in 25 % of cases). HWS showed a lower buffer area ratio, in general, than the other types of vegetative barriers, and in most of the experiments they had a width of 10-m.

Fig. 5 depicts the runoff trapping efficiency in relation to the condition of the non-buffer area. As expected, overall runoff trapping efficiency was higher in experiments with a vegetative barrier at the end of a bare soil plot, 53.4 %, than in those with a covered plot above the barrier, 33.5 %. In both ground cover types on the plot, the upstream areas seem to be well distributed in relation to buffer width, buffer area ratio and plot slope values (Fig. 5(a), (b), (c)).

3.3. Sediment trapping efficiency

Sediment trapping efficiency for the whole dataset evaluated averaged 62.6 %, higher than the runoff trapping efficiency (40.1 %), and with a greater range of variation, from –109 to 100 % (Table S3). As in the case of runoff trapping efficiency, it should be noted that four studies reported negative values of sediment reduction; that is, the values of sediment loss were higher in the plot with a vegetative barrier than in the bare plot, although none of these four studies were in arid or semi-arid regions (Fig. 6). Sediment trapping efficiency in arid and semi-arid regions tended to be higher than in humid regions (Kruskal-Wallis H test, $p = 0.0001$; Table 2 and S3; Fig. 6), averaging 77.6 vs. 55.1 % (median value 85 vs. 63 %), ranging from 36 to 100 % and from –109 to 99.9 % for arid or semi-arid and humid regions, respectively. Also, the standard deviation was higher in humid regions (36.4%) than semi-arid and arid regions (17.9%). This is in line with the trend observed for runoff trapping efficiency. Fig. 6(a) shows the reduction in sediment loss due to the vegetative barrier according to the width of the barrier, distinguishing between humid or arid and semi-arid climatic

Fig. 4. Relationship between runoff trapping efficiency (%) and: (a) vegetative buffer width (m); (b) buffer area ratio (vegetative buffer area/plot area; dimensionless), and (c) slope of the plot (%), by type of buffer strip (herbaceous, HS; woody, WS; herbaceous-woody combination, HWS, and block strip, BLS). Number of data points: (a) 102 HS, 46 WS, 15 HWS, 2 BLS; (b) 82 HS, 45 WS, 4 HWS, 2 BLS, and (c) 96 HS, 46 WS, 14 HWS, 2 BLS.

conditions. As in the case of runoff trapping efficiency, there was an overall trend towards higher sediment trapping efficiency with increasing width of the vegetative barrier, albeit with a large variability within each width. Experiments in arid and semi-arid regions have been carried out in plots tending to have a higher

vegetative barrier area ratio (usually above 0.5; Fig. 6(b)). As already indicated for runoff, this higher ratio could explain, partly, the greater sediment trapping efficiency by the vegetative barrier in arid and semi-arid regions, despite the steeper slope on which these experiments have been carried out as compared to humid

Fig. 5. Relationship between runoff trapping efficiency (%) and: a) vegetative buffer width (m); b) buffer area ratio (vegetative buffer area/plot area; dimensionless), and c) slope of the plot (%), by soil protection of the non-buffer area (bare soil, BS, and non-bare soil, NBS). Number of data points: a) 53 BS, 112 NBS; b) 42 BS, 47 NBS, and c) 46 BS, 112 NBS.

regions (Fig. 6(c)).

Overall, the sediment trapping efficiency was significantly higher than the runoff trapping efficiency (Fig. 6(d)), with the two dependent variables significantly correlated ($y = 0.693x + 34.47$; $n = 147$; $r^2 = 0.62$; Pearson correlation coefficient = 0.78;

$p < 0.001$), without statistical differences between both climate regions.

Fig. 7 explores the effect on sediment trapping efficiency of vegetation type in the buffer strip. The type of vegetation in the buffer strip had a similar behaviour regarding sediment trapping

Fig. 6. Relationship between sediment trapping efficiency (%) and: a) vegetative buffer width (m); b) buffer area ratio (vegetative buffer area/plot area; dimensionless); c) slope of the plot (%), and d) runoff trapping efficiency (%), by climate type (humid, HU, and semi-arid or arid, SA–A). Number of data points: a) 114 HU, 50 SA–A; b) 104 HU, 46 SA–A; c) 110 HU, 47 SA–A, and d) 97 HU, 53 SA–A.

than that observed for runoff reduction, with an average value of sediment trapping efficiency slightly lower for herbaceous vegetation (HS) that for all the combinations including woody vegetation (MS), 59.5 vs. 67.4 %, respectively, with statistically significant differences (Table 2). When analysed by the different woody vegetation types, WS and HWS (average sediment trapping efficiency of 67.5 and 61.0 %, respectively) showed the same trend as that observed for runoff trapping efficiency, without significant differences.

In general, the runoff and sediment trapping efficiencies had a very similar distribution of dimension variables for each type of vegetation, as they belong to the same studies. We did not observe statistically significant differences in sediment trapping efficiency between those experiments with bare or covered soil in the area upstream of the vegetative barrier (Table 2).

3.4. Nutrients trapping efficiency

The effect of vegetation type on phosphorus trapping efficiency was statistically significant (Table 2), with a trend similar to that observed for runoff trapping efficiency. So, HS presented an average P trapping efficiency of 39.5 %, with average values of 68.7 and 34.7 % for WS and HWS, respectively. Overall, a slight correlation of phosphorus trapping efficiency with the vegetative barrier width was observed (Pearson correlation coefficient = 0.30, $p = 0.009$)

(Fig. 8(a)), and none between nitrogen trapping efficiency and the barrier width (Pearson correlation coefficient = -0.095 , $p = 0.52$) (Fig. S1). Due to the few articles available, the distribution of the vegetative barrier dimension variables was limited (Fig. 8(a), (b), (c)). No effect of vegetation type, or any other variable, on nitrogen trapping efficiency was detected (Table 2; Fig. S1). As it occurs in the sediment and runoff trapping efficiencies, a large variability in the P and N trapping efficiencies was found.

Phosphorus trapping efficiency was higher than that of nitrogen, 44.9 vs. 38.4 %, respectively (Fig. 9(a) and Table S3).

3.5. Probability distribution function of sediment trapping efficiency

Fig. 10 shows the normalised cumulative probability distribution function for the two climatic regions separately. This allows an interpretation of the results, and it might provide insight into most expected outcomes. Fig. 10 shows how, based on available experimental data, sediment trapping efficiency in humid conditions presented a tailed distribution, with a relatively high probability (around 10 %) of not contributing to sediment reduction (normalised trapping efficiency <0), with the remaining 90 % of cases having an efficiency spread between 0 and 175 %, approximately, respect to the average value. In the majority of the reported studies (approximately 60 %) was presented a sediment trapping efficiency

Fig. 7. Relationship between sediment trapping efficiency (%) and: (a) vegetative buffer width; (b) buffer area ratio (vegetative buffer area/plot area; dimensionless), and (c) slope of the plot, by type of buffer strip (herbaceous HS; woody, WS; herbaceous-woody combination, HWS, and block strip, BLS). Number of data points: (a) 102 HS, 54 WS, 6 HWS, 2 BLS; (b) 91 HS, 52 WS, 4 HWS, 2 BLS, and (c) 96 HS, 54 WS, 5 HWS, 2 BLS.

Fig. 8. Relationship between phosphorus trapping efficiency (%) and: (a) vegetative buffer width (m); (b) buffer area ratio (vegetative buffer area/plot area; dimensionless), and (c) slope of the plot (%), by type of buffer strip (herbaceous, HS; woody, WS; herbaceous-woody combination, HWS, and block strip, BLS). Number of data points: (a) 44 HS, 13 WS, 15 HWS, 2 BLS; (b) 30 HS, 13 WS, 4 HWS, 2 BLS, and (c) 44 HS, 13 WS, 14 HWS, 2 BLS.

higher than 100 % (average value). In comparison, the results found in arid and semi-arid areas showed a much narrower distribution of sediment trapping, with efficiencies ranging from 40 to 125 %, approximately. Approximately the same proportion of reported experiments in arid and semi-arid areas, around 60 %, presented a normalised sediment trapping efficiency higher than 100 % (average value). The shape of the normalised cumulative probability distribution function allows fitting to a fourth-degree polynomial equations $[y = A + B \cdot x + C \cdot x^2 + D \cdot x^3 + E \cdot x^4]$. Fig. 10 show the equations obtained to represent arid and semi-arid ($A = -1.02, B = 4.70, C = -7.43, D = 5.01, E = -0.859$), and humid ($A = 0.077, B = 0.153, C = 0.166, D = 0.035, E = -0.0098$) environments show a good fit (adjusted $R^2 = 0.994$ & 0.996 , respectively).

Fig. 11 shows the average values of the sediment trapping

efficiency for a given vegetative barrier width and the two climatic regions. For the semi-arid and arid areas, an apparent logarithmic correlation with the width of the vegetative barrier was shown, albeit with a moderate predictive power ($r^2 = 0.45$). For the humid areas, a similar logarithmic correlation was shown, with a lower predictive power ($r^2 = 0.27$).

Since the most operational variable for designing and implanting a vegetative barrier is the barrier width, we deepen our analysis of the probability distribution of sediment trapping efficiency for different barrier width classes, according to the available data (Fig. 12). In semi-arid and arid regions, we have two width ranges with enough data to determine a probability distribution: between 0.25 and 0.5-m; and between 2.75 and 3.0-m. In humid regions, we select five width ranges: 0.9–1.0-m; 2.0–2.3-m; 5.0–6.0-m; 10.0-m, and 15.0–15.3-m. This can provide preliminary insight on the expected yield of a vegetative barrier based on climate conditions and barrier width. The fitting performed for these functions is shown in Table S5, and it was also adjusted a fourth-degree polynomial equation, with good fits above adjusted $R^2 > 0.98$. These probability distribution functions, which we used as a probabilistic model, are complemented with the average trapping efficiency (Fig. 11). Fig. 10 or 12 might be used to estimate the trapping efficiency, from the general probabilistic distribution or for a determined width range, respectively.

4. Discussion

4.1. Exploratory analysis

Before analysing and discussing the results, it is necessary to note the limited presence of articles on arid and semi-arid regions in previous reviews. Also, the fact that these reviews rely in a large extend on similar empirical studies. For instance, Borin et al. (2005), one of these reviews, appears as a major source in eight out of the nine reviews found. They provide very useful insight on the variability of trapping efficiency and its relationship with structural features of the barriers like, e.g. width or composition of vegetation, but our work helps to deepen this analysis contributing the potential effect of different climate conditions.

Our results showed that the type of rainfall used in the experiment, natural or simulated, significantly affected the results (Table 1). There is an overall trend to report higher trapping efficiency in studies using simulated rain or runoff, around 8 % higher for runoff, 5 % for sediment, 27 % for phosphorus and 21 % for nitrogen. These differences can be attributed to two main factors. One is that rainfall simulation experiments are performed under more controlled conditions and in relatively short time, and therefore can be biased towards being performed in vegetative barriers in the best possible conditions. This is more difficult to achieve with natural rainfall experiments, which have a longer duration, usually more than one year (e.g. Kiepe, 1996; Shiono et al., 2007). During this time, the vegetative barrier might present different growing stages as well as the effect of different stresses, like drought, rill erosion, changes in barrier management, etc., which might affect its efficiency (McKergow et al., 2003). The other factor is the higher and more homogeneous rainfall intensity used during rainfall simulations as compared to natural rainfall experiments where a spectrum of rainfall intensities happens. This suggests that although rainfall simulation experiments are extremely interesting for providing insight on the mechanisms involved in the use of vegetative barriers to reduce hydrologic connectivity, the efficiency values obtained from them can overestimate their actual efficiency under field conditions with natural rainfall. For this reason, after the exploratory analysis, we concentrated our further analysis on experiments from natural rainfall, which is not a strategy pursued

Fig. 9. Relationship between phosphorus trapping efficiency (%) and: (a) nitrogen trapping efficiency (%; n = 51), and (b) sediment trapping efficiency (%; n = 45).

in previous reviews (e.g. Gumiere et al., 2011).

Another variable that also proved to have a significant effect on the trapping effectiveness was the type of experimental measure used. Basically, paired plots using a control without a vegetative barrier vs. other type of measurements (e.g. sediment traps along the slope before and after the vegetative barrier). Overall, experiments using paired plots reported 22 % higher trapping efficiency for runoff, 10 % lower for sediment and 20 % lower for nitrogen as compared to other types of measurements. This might be due again

to the relatively longer duration of the paired plot experiments as compared to those using other technologies or measures, for reasons discussed before which allow a better integration of overall field conditions. The paired plots provide an integrated measure of what happens in the whole area, while most of the other technologies rely on point measurements that need to be subjected to further calculation and assumptions, e.g. contributing area, to provide an overall figure of trapping efficiency, showing a higher uncertainty. This result also suggests that a careful appraisal of the

Fig. 10. Cumulative probability distribution function of normalised sediment trapping efficiency by climate type (humid, HU, and semi-arid and arid, SA–A). Lines show the fitting of the cumulative probability distribution function to a fourth-degree polynomial equation [$y = A + B \cdot x + C \cdot x^2 + D \cdot x^3 + E \cdot x^4$]: orange line for semi-arid and arid ($A = -1.02, B = 4.70, C = -7.43, D = 5.01, E = -0.859$, adjusted $R^2 = 0.994$) and green line for humid ($A = 0.077, B = 0.153, C = 0.166, D = 0.035, E = -0.0098$, adjusted $R^2 = 0.996$).

measurement technique used in the studies needs to be considered to avoid overestimation of trapping efficiency under field conditions.

The analysis of the results from natural rainfall events and paired plots (Table 2) showed how the type of climate in the area where the experiment was carried out had significant effect on the measured efficiency. Experiments in arid and semi-arid climate reported a higher trapping efficiency of the vegetative barriers, 33 % for runoff and 23 % for sediment as compared to humid climate. This reflects the effect of different rainfall depth, lower in arid and semi-arid areas, and intensity in different types of climate, as well as different vegetation types and growth under different climate conditions. Vegetation type, mix strip (MS) or herbaceous (HS), only presented a significant, but moderate, effect on sediment reduction efficiency, 6 % higher in MS. This might reflect that in

many of the experiments evaluated, the combination of woody and herbaceous vegetation might provide a denser vegetative barrier with higher sediment retention potential.

4.2. Runoff trapping efficiency

Confronting runoff trapping efficiency with the vegetative barrier dimension variables (buffer width, buffer area ratio, and slope of the plot) slight trends were apparent but without any significant correlation (Fig. 3) for any climate condition. Our interpretation is that the variability among experiments introduced by numerous uncontrolled variables (e.g. spatial variability within the barrier in terms of vegetation, soil and microtopography; different age of the barriers; specific rainfall conditions; ...) overcome the effect of the dimension variables on the experimental results, producing a high variability. We explored the combined effect of the dimension variables using a multiple regression analysis, not shown, which hardly improved correlation with the runoff trapping efficiency of the barriers. Coupled with this, is the fact that most of the reviewed studies have a limited number of replications of each treatment, between 1 and 3 usually, which exacerbates the difficulty of handling the variability among plots. This situation is well known in runoff plot studies where high coefficients of variation have been reported, in the range of 30–50 % for seasonal runoff (Rüttimann et al., 1995), even in experiments with a large number of replications, like Wendt et al. (1986), who reported a coefficient of variation (CV) of 30 % in annual runoff, in an experiment with 40 replicated plots.

The few experiments found in our review with a larger number of plots test different classes with each variable, e.g. sowing dose (Hall et al., 1983), plant species of the vegetative barrier (Uusi-Kämpä, 2005), locations (Patty et al., 1997), different years or seasons (Cullum et al., 2007), which result in a reduced number of replications. Both issues are complicated to address, particularly for different teams working for different funding agencies and with specific objectives, but some basic guidelines might be extracted. One is that perhaps it will be worth considering that teams setting new experiments try to replicate some of the most used designs to allow a better comparison of their results with those of previous studies. The other is that given the large heterogeneity among the

Fig. 11. Logarithmic trend of the average sediment trapping efficiency (%) by climate (humid, HU, and semi-arid and arid, SA–A) regarding of the vegetative strip width (m). Number of data points: 23 HU (blue dots), 6 SA–A (red dots).

Fig. 12. Cumulative probability distribution function of normalised sediment trapping efficiency according to the width of the buffer strip, in: a) semi-arid and arid areas, with vegetative buffer width between 0.25 and 0.5 m (brown dots) and between 2.75 and 3.0 m (green dots), and b) humid areas, with vegetative buffer width between 0.9 and 1.0 m (brown dots), between 2.0 and 2.3 m (orange dots), between 5.0 and 6.0 m (grey dots), width of 10 m (green dots) and between 15.0 and 15.3 m (blue dots).

replicated plots, it might be worth trying to optimize the number of replications at the expense of reducing the number of treatments, since the probability of detecting significant differences in treatments in which changes in barrier dimensions are small and slim.

On the other side, we detected significant differences in runoff trapping efficiency in relation to the type of climate. We can only speculate on some of the reasons for this, see below, but it suggests that we should be aware of this when trying to extrapolate any kind of individual or review study. A careful observation of the results indicates that the majority of negative trapping efficiencies, which means that the plot without the vegetative barrier had a lower runoff, sediment or nutrient losses, occurred in humid climate, decreasing the overall values. Experiments in humid climates will have a higher probability of a saturated, or close to saturation, conditions in the soil profile during the runoff events, resulting in more saturation-induced runoff events (Dunne & Black, 1970) as compared to experiments in arid and semi-arid areas. This

mechanism might lessen the efficiency of vegetative barriers in reducing runoff and related fluxes, as compared to the arid and semi-arid areas. Thus, although a wet soil condition most of the time allows for better vegetation growth, it would not reflect into less runoff, being able to observe more runoff (Srivastava et al., 2022). In addition, some differences among the plots due to spatial variability, discussed in the previous paragraph, might result in a higher change of negative trapping efficiency. On the contrary, situations of infiltration-excess runoff (Dunne & Black, 1970) are more probable in arid and semi-arid climates, and in these situations the effectiveness in reducing runoff and related fluxes should be theoretically higher.

The type of plant species used in the vegetative barrier showed to have a significant effect on the overall runoff trapping efficiency (Fig. 4 and Table 2). Mixed herbaceous and woody vegetation barriers (HWS) showed the lowest average runoff efficiency, 20.7%, as compared to herbaceous (HS) and woody (WS) barriers, with

average efficiencies of 36.7 and 53.8 % respectively. This was so, despite the fact that HS presented a larger number of experiments with negative efficiencies across different barrier widths. Although we can't be conclusive, it might be possible that HWS might ensure a minimum reduction in runoff as compared to the control plot, probably for the combination of species that might have a synergistic effect in terms of improving infiltration and lowering soil moisture in the area of the vegetative barrier. For reasons we do not fully understand, HWS do not achieve high runoff efficiencies. It might be related to the saturation excess overland flow over a long period, since most of these experiments were located in a cold and humid type of climate.

WS presented a higher efficiency in reducing runoff, as compared to the other two types (HS and HWS). This might be due to a higher effectiveness in improving water infiltration into soil due to a deeper root system. In fact, Douglas-Mankin et al. (2021) showed that infiltration processes in vegetative barriers can be more important than other variables, such as their width. Experiments of WS were approximately equally distributed between the two types of climates used in our classification (humid vs. arid and semi-arid), so we discard an unintended bias due to climate type. HS tend to have a broader range of runoff trapping efficiency, probably reflecting, in some situations, lower effectiveness of the root system to improve infiltration, as compared to woody vegetation. This fact, together with the suspected variability of the vegetation density data in the different experiments with HS, could explain part of this lower runoff trapping efficiency. Also, most of the studies did not consider the orientation of the slope. Overall, it is necessary to provide better information on the actual vegetation density of the vegetative barrier during the duration of the experiments. Our results contrast with the few previous individual studies comparing different vegetation types, understood herbaceous vs. some wood or woody/herbaceous mix. Very few of these studies identified significant differences in runoff trapping efficiency between herbaceous and some kind of woody or woody-herbaceous mix vegetation (e.g. Duchemin & Hogue, 2009; Uusi-Kämpä & Jauhainen, 2010). This suggests that our analysis has captured an overall trend, which might be difficult to detect at local conditions without an experiment with well established vegetation and a sufficient number of replications to overcome spatial variability and other sources of variability among treatments (like variability of species within each vegetation type).

The condition of the non-buffer area significantly affects runoff trapping efficiency. A non-buffer area with bare soil had a higher runoff trapping efficiency, 53.4 %, as compared to a non-buffer area covered with vegetation, 33.5 %. This can be explained because a bare soil plot tends to have higher runoff than vegetation covered plots (e.g. Garcia-Estringana et al., 2013; Hudek et al., 2014). As a result, differences in runoff generation between the control and the treatment plot tend to be smaller in the case of the covered plots, and so reducing runoff trapping efficiency. This is also reflected by that most of the experiments with negative trapping efficiencies observed corresponded to the non-buffer area with some type of cover.

4.3. Sediment trapping efficiency

Confronting sediment trapping efficiency with the dimension variables of the vegetative barriers (buffer width, buffer area ratio and slope of the plot) slight trends were apparent but without any clear correlation under any climate condition (Fig. 6). This behaviour, similar to what we found for runoff trapping efficiency (see Section 4.2.), was also reported in previous studies (e.g. Gumiere et al., 2011). The high variability, the limited number of replications, or the single average values from the reviewed studies in this

work, might disguise the correlation of sediment trapping with these dimension variables. A multiple regression analysis with the combined effect of the dimension variables as in runoff trapping efficiency (not shown) neither showed correlations. Previous studies reported a high CV for soil erosion, similar to runoff, near 30 % (Bryan & Luk, 1981). Nearing et al. (1999) showed that both for individual rain events or annual records, the relative differences in erosion between replicated plots decrease with higher measured soil loss values (14 % for a soil loss of 20 kg m⁻² and 150 % for a loss less than 0.01 kg m⁻²). This fact, added to the heterogeneity among replications, as occur in runoff trapping efficiency, generates difficulties in the relationship between dimensions variables and sediment trapping efficiency.

The climatic zones affect significantly the sediment trapping efficiency (Fig. 6). Higher sediment trapping efficiencies were obtained in semi-arid or arid regions, 77.6 %, compared to humid regions, 55.1 %, as all negative sediment trapping efficiencies occurred in humid regions. These results may be due to the different rain distribution and intensity patterns between the two climate types. In humid regions, precipitation distribution is more homogeneous, so soil moisture conditions are usually close to saturation, which would lead to higher runoff. On the other hand, in semi-arid and arid regions, precipitation is mainly concentrated during autumn and spring, with isolated storm events. In this case, soil is unsaturated during most of the time and therefore water infiltration capacity is higher. Also, the annual precipitation influences the sediment yield in an area. Langbein & Schumm (1958) quantified the non-linear relationship between effective precipitation and sediment yield. Arid and semi-arid climates erode the soil more despite having a low annual rainfall. This fact, combined with the reduction of flow rates by the vegetative barrier, would favour a better sediment trapping efficiency in semi-arid and arid regions.

The process of water erosion can explain the relationship between runoff and sediment trapping efficiencies. In the first place, a degradation of the soil aggregates occurs through the kinetic energy of the raindrops. The generated runoff will transport the smaller particles. The greater the intensity of the runoff, the greater its drag force, which will lead to greater soil erosion. The trend showed that the runoff trapping efficiency is lower than the sediment trapping efficiency (Fig. 6(d)). In fact, many authors have discussed the relationship between runoff and sediment trapping efficiency. Fox & Sabbagh (2009) obtained an exponential relationship, with a regression parameter $b = 0.04$ ($r^2 = 0.51$). Using their relationship with the data from this review (without considering negative trapping efficiencies), we obtained $r^2 = 0.50$ (Fig. S2). Fitting b , our best approximation was with $b = 0.017$ ($r^2 = 0.55$). With an analysis of outliers, a value of b between 0.04 and 0.017 can explain most of the half of our data relationship.

Regarding the type of vegetation, negative sediment trapping efficiencies in herbaceous strips (HS) were less than the observed for runoff trapping efficiency, although in average (Table 2), is slightly higher for woody strips (WS). WS presented the highest average sediment efficiency, 67.5 %, compared to HS and HWS, with average efficiencies of 59.5 and 61.0 %, respectively (Fig. 7). Some issues of these differences have been discussed extensively in the runoff trapping efficiency section. This might be because in WS, the root system of the plant species is deeper, reducing runoff speed, increasing water infiltration and therefore sediments dragged by the runoff.

The condition of the non-buffer area does not affect significantly sediment trapping efficiency. A non-buffer area with bare soil had a higher sediment trapping efficiency, 68.9 %, as compared to a vegetated non-buffer area, 58.5 %, as the runoff trapping efficiency.

4.4. Nutrients trapping efficiency

No clear correlations were found between nutrient trapping efficiencies and experimental variables, except phosphorus and type of vegetation (Table 2). Nutrients showed similar transport processes to sediment and runoff, and consequently the large variability observed in the latter two was also found in nutrient trapping efficiencies, as discussed in previous sections. Additionally, the number of experimental plots measuring nutrient trapping was much lower than the ones for runoff and sediment trapping: 74 and 48 for phosphorus and nitrogen, respectively, compared to 168 for runoff and 167 for sediment trapping efficiency. In fact, no experimental plots were found in semi-arid and arid regions for the case of nutrients.

In general, in humid climates, vegetative barriers contributed to nutrient trapping efficiencies, with positive results on average. Phosphorus trapping efficiency was higher than nitrogen, 44.9 vs. 38.4 %, respectively (Fig. 9(a)). The dynamics of phosphorus and nitrogen are distinct, where the movement of sediment-bound P is the majority (Kleinman et al., 2011). So, this can be attributed to the different processes involved in their transport, in the case of P more related to sediment transport (Fig. 9(b)) as compared to N.

Regarding phosphorus trapping efficiency, significant differences were only observed with the type of vegetation (Fig. 8). WS showed the highest average phosphorus trapping efficiency, 68.7 %, compared to HS and HWS, with average efficiencies of 39.5 and 34.7 %, respectively. However, all the experimental plots with WS belong to the study by Anderson et al. (2020). This fact should be considered, as this study only assessed a continuously grazing plot compared to a fenced riparian strip formed by trees.

The slight positive trend between phosphorus trapping and buffer width agrees when the experimental works are analysed individually. Dorioz et al. (2006) showed how each experiment obtained a different percentage of phosphorus trapping, but with this trend until the width reaches an optimal range. Also, they showed how the vegetation type generates differences despite having the same plot characteristics. When all the experiments are analysed as a set, the variability reduces the possibility of finding some kind of trend.

4.5. Probability distribution function of sediment trapping efficiency

To our knowledge, the existing models trying to determine trapping efficiency by filter strips are complex and mainly used for academic purposes (Ramler et al., 2022), and the number of datasets, and the combination of more and different dimension variables, would lead to different results and accuracy (Rodríguez, 1997) and therefore to complex probabilistic models.

It is crucial to identify the difficulty level of the probabilistic model to develop it simple enough for a farmer or technician when interested in implementing vegetative barriers in agricultural landscapes (Brodt et al., 2009). Moreover, the use of GIS methodology can help to make it more visual. Mahoney et al. (2018) parameterized the probability of sediment connectivity with the presence or not of a buffer with a binary system. If we aim to use a binary system with buffer strips, when it exists, the sediment will not pass and vice versa if the buffer strip does not exist.

One attempt at helping decision-making is the one by Liu et al. (2017). They developed a probabilistic distribution for the trapping efficiency of phosphorus, nitrogen and sediment when agricultural best management practices (including vegetative barriers) were implemented, obtaining trapping efficiencies over 0 % in all the cases. However, in our study, the main aim is to focus on one of these best management practices.

The combination of Figs. 10–12 describes the probabilistic model for sediment trapping efficiency with the width of vegetative barriers, as it is the easiest design parameter to modify and interpret by farmers and technicians. The mean value of trapping efficiency for a given width and climate could be obtained from the function in Fig. 11. In a second step, the variability of the experimental data can be summarized, and introduced in design studies, using cumulative distribution functions (e.g. Fig. 10). Fitting each of the climatic regions to a fourth-degree polynomial equation allows us to quantify and strengthen our appraisal of the sediment trapping efficiency for modelling and design purposes. Fig. 6(a) show how sediment trapping efficiency values are vertically clustered at specific widths, reflecting the widths used in the empirical studies. For the given case (sediment trapping efficiency as a function of the width of the vegetative barrier and differentiated by climate) it is possible to use specific functions if the width is within the ranges exposed (Fig. 12). Based on the distribution shown in Fig. 10, vegetative barriers in humid regions could fail with negative trapping efficiencies in 8 % of the cases. However, no negative trapping efficiencies were detected in arid and semi-arid regions as far as the vegetative barrier is well established. Moreover, 94 % of the available data in arid and semi-arid climates is from vegetative barriers with a width less than 4-m, so only this interval is properly represented compared to wider strips (Fig. 6(a)). In both climates, a logarithmic relationship shows a r^2 between 0.27 and 0.45 (Fig. 11), similar to previous reviews (Liu et al., 2008; Yuan et al., 2009). These low predictive results suggest the need of an alternative strategy. This alternative strategy, which is the one proposed in this manuscript, synthesises sediment trapping efficiency data for different ranges of barrier width classes (see Table S5) and for each width class and climate type to determine a normalised probability distribution function. These functions (described in Table S5) are similar to the one presented for all the barriers width aggregated for each climate type, for simplicity, in Fig. 10. We opted for this approach because it keeps reflecting the effect of climate and barrier width to the extent supported by empirical observations. Fig. 12 shows the probabilistic model based on vegetative barrier width intervals considering the different climatic regions. For a given width, anyone interested in the plantation of a vegetative barrier will be able to estimate the average sediment trapping efficiency and, subsequently, the probability reached for one efficiency. In semi-arid and arid regions, the intervals from 0.25 to 0.5-m and from 2.75 to 3.0-m width had an average value of sediment trapping efficiency of 73.5 and 82.4 %, respectively. In humid regions, the average values of sediment trapping efficiency were 41.8, 35.2, 80.2, 53.5 and 49.7 % for width intervals of 0.9–1.0-m, 2.0–2.3-m, 5.0–6.0-m, 10.0-m, and 15.0–15.3-m, respectively.

Although general recommendations for controlling erosion using vegetative barriers contemplate widths between 12 and 14-m (Schultz et al., 2009), the dataset used in this study assessed this specific range as impossible for both climatic zones. In humid climates, narrow strips (<2.3-m) showed the lowest sediment trapping efficiencies. However, we keep finding negative values in the range with the widest vegetative barriers (around 15-m), which could explain why the highest average trapping efficiency is not within this width range. These negative values appears in the study of Pilon et al. (2017), who compared plots using different management practices, one of them with an herbaceous buffer strip of 15.3-m. They obtained sediment trapping efficiencies ranging from –15 to 82 % despite the width of the strip, due to other factors such as management practices. The negative values appear in consecutive years where the non-buffer area was fertilized, so the authors suggested that vegetation production was likely lower in the unfertilized area, which would result in less sediment trapping efficiency by the herbaceous strip.

This type of probabilistic models would be more reliable if the results showed more homogeneity. Xiao et al. (2011) studied how a 0.5-m wide vegetative barrier can behave according to simulated rainfall, with different plant species, percentage coverage of the non-buffer area, and plot slope, with three repetitions. With a probabilistic view, the number of repetitions maybe is not enough in this instance. In addition to a higher number of repetitions, studies assessing these behaviours should focus on fewer variables to delimit the driving variables.

5. Conclusions

This manuscript has shown an in-depth review of studies on the efficiency of vegetative barriers on runoff, sediment and nutrients reduction in overland flow across various climate. It has not been possible to compare nutrient trapping efficiency by climate, with no available data in semi-arid and arid zones. The efficacy of vegetative barriers in trapping runoff and sediment is well documented in humid regions, with averages of 29.6 and 55.1 %, respectively. Although they appeared at a lower rate in the scientific literature, vegetative barriers in semi-arid and arid regions seem to present a remarkable efficiency, averages of 62.9 and 78.6 % for runoff and sediment trapping efficiency respectively. They can provide an alternative, or complement, to cover crops in agricultural areas to reduce water erosion, particularly in arid areas where cover crops can be complicated to implement.

The variability in the efficiency of trapping runoff, sediment and nutrients by vegetative barriers is relevant due to environmental conditions and design characteristics of the experiment. Design variables, such as vegetation type, the origin of precipitation, or the type of measurement of trapping efficiency, can determine different results. The vegetation type of the vegetative barrier has shown to be a significant variable in the trapping efficiencies, a higher trapping efficiency has been observed in woody strips compared to herbaceous strips in sediment (67.5 and 60 %) and runoff (53.8 and 36.7 %).

In our previous analysis we observed significant differences in the origin of the rainfall. A significant proportion of trials have been carried out under controlled conditions, which our analysis deleted. These trials might distort reality when we implement vegetative barriers in actual field conditions. It is apparent from our review the need for more experimental trials in dry areas with natural rainfall and also a better description of climate conditions (precipitation, evapotranspiration, ...) in all the studies on vegetative barriers. Generating more useful knowledge on the use of vegetative barriers against erosion and particles movement in arid or semi-arid climates is a relevant issue, as there are more limiting factors (rainfall distribution, water stress, vegetation density, etc.) than in humid climates. The way to estimate these trapping efficiencies and the nature of the rain can generate results with significant differences due to large variability. Although there are many variables of a different nature in vegetative barriers (environmental, experimental or vegetative), buffer width, vegetation type and climate are the most dominant variables from our study.

The probabilistic model between trapping efficiencies and dimension variables is a practical tool for its incorporation into different modelling approaches. A vegetative barrier could collapse with negative trapping efficiencies in 8 % of the cases in humid climates and never collapse in semi-arid and arid regions. Widths of 5–10 m in humid regions have a very high sediment trapping efficiency, emphasizing the effectiveness of vegetative barriers for controlling sediment losses at landscape scale when properly implemented. While this trapping efficiency is affected by multiple factors (e.g. buffer width or the slope of the plot), previous reviews obtained some trends but with a large variability. Using probability

distribution highlights this variability, emphasizing the need for closer control over variables in experimental trials for more reliable probabilistic models across different variables.

Pairing this methodology with GIS could include results of probability distribution functions to determine the hydrological connectivity for runoff, sediments, nutrients or pollutants, based on existing data. This strategy based on probability to handle variability in efficiency can be a valuable tool, although further research can help to enlarge its scope and reduce uncertainty. For this, it is necessary to continue carrying out empirical studies under different climates, particularly in arid and semi-arid to assess correctly how vegetative barriers behave and how they potentially can be improved. For this, better information on climate and vegetation density during the experiment are of paramount relevance.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

José-Antonio Muñoz: Data curation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Methodology, Visualization, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. **Gema Guzmán:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Supervision, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. **María-Auxiliadora Soriano:** Supervision, Visualization, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. **José A. Gómez:** Conceptualization, Funding acquisition, Methodology, Supervision, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests:

Jose Antonio Munoz Sanchez reports financial support was provided by Spanish Ministry of Science and Innovation. Jose Alfonso Gomez Calero reports financial support was provided by Spanish Ministry of Science and Innovation. Jose Alfonso Gomez Calero reports financial support was provided by European Union's Horizon 2020.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.iswcr.2023.12.001>.

References

- Abu-Zreig, M., Rudra, R. P., Lalonde, M. N., Whiteley, H. R., & Kaushik, N. K. (2004). Experimental investigation of runoff reduction and sediment removal by vegetated filter strips. *Hydrological Processes*, 18(11), 2029–2037. <https://doi.org/10.1002/hyp.1400>
- Anderson, K. R., Moore, P. A., Pilon, C., Martin, J. W., Pote, D. H., Owens, P. R., et al.

- (2020). Long-term effects of grazing management and buffer strips on phosphorus runoff from pastures fertilized with poultry litter. *Journal of Environmental Quality*, 49(1), 85–96. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jeq2.20010>
- Batista, P., Fiener, P., Scheper, S., & Alewell, C. (2022). A conceptual model-based sediment connectivity assessment for patchy agricultural catchments. *Hydrology and Earth System Sciences Discussions*, 26(14), 3753–3770. <https://doi.org/10.5194/hess-26-3753-2022>
- Borin, M., Vianello, M., Morari, F., & Zanin, G. (2005). Effectiveness of buffer strips in removing pollutants in runoff from a cultivated field in North-East Italy. *Agriculture, Ecosystems & Environment*, 105(1–2), 101–114. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agee.2004.05.011>
- Brodth, S., Klonsky, K., Jackson, L., Brush, S. B., & Smukler, S. (2009). Factors affecting adoption of hedgerows and other biodiversity-enhancing features on farms in California, USA. *Agroforestry Systems*, 76(1), 195–206. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10457-008-9168-8>
- Bryan, R. B., & Luk, S. H. (1981). Laboratory experiments on the variation of soil erosion under simulated rainfall. *Geoderma*, 26(4), 245–265. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0016-7061\(81\)90023-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/0016-7061(81)90023-9)
- Burguet, M., Guzmán, G., de Luna, E., Taguas, E. V., & Gómez, J. A. (2018). Evaluation of disruption of sediment connectivity and herbicide transport across a slope by grass strips using a magnetic iron oxide tracer. *Soil and Tillage Research*, 180, 268–281. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.still.2018.02.014>
- Christen, B., & Dalgaard, T. (2013). Buffers for biomass production in temperate European agriculture: A review and synthesis on function, ecosystem services and implementation. *Biomass and Bioenergy*, 55, 53–67. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biombioe.2012.09.053>
- Cole, L. J., Stockan, J., & Helliwell, R. (2020). Managing riparian buffer strips to optimise ecosystem services: A review. *Agriculture, Ecosystems & Environment*, 296, Article 106891. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agee.2020.106891>
- Cullum, R. F., Wilson, G. V., McGregor, K. C., & Johnson, J. R. (2007). Runoff and soil loss from ultra-narrow row cotton plots with and without stiff-grass hedges. *Soil and Tillage Research*, 93(1), 56–63. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.still.2006.03.010>
- Dorioz, J. M., Wang, D., Poulencard, J., & Trévisan, D. (2006). The effect of grass buffer strips on phosphorus dynamics—A critical review and synthesis as a basis for application in agricultural landscapes in France. *Agriculture, Ecosystems & Environment*, 117(1), 4–21. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agee.2006.03.029>
- Douglas-Mankin, K. R., Helmers, M. J., & Harmel, R. D. (2021). Review of filter strip performance and function for improving water quality from agricultural lands. *Transactions of the ASABE*, 64(2), 659–674. <https://doi.org/10.13031/TRANSL.14169>. American Society of Agricultural and Biological Engineers.
- Duchemin, M., & Hogue, R. (2009). Reduction in agricultural non-point source pollution in the first year following establishment of an integrated grass/tree filter strip system in southern Quebec (Canada). *Agriculture, Ecosystems & Environment*, 131(1–2), 85–97. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agee.2008.10.005>
- Dufková, J. (2007). Determination of wind erosion next to shelterbelts. *Acta Universitatis Agriculturae et Silviculturae Mendelianae Brunensis*, 55(5), 65–70. <https://doi.org/10.1118/actaun200755050065>
- Dunne, T., & Black, R. D. (1970). An experimental investigation of runoff production in permeable soils. *Water Resources Research*, 6(2), 478–490. <https://doi.org/10.1029/WR006i002p00478>
- Durán, V. H., Rodríguez, C. R., Francia Martínez, J. R., Martínez Raya, A., Arroyo, L., Cárceles, B., et al. (2008). Benefits of plant strips for sustainable mountain agriculture. *Agronomy for Sustainable Development*, 28(4), 497–505. <https://doi.org/10.1051/agro:2008020>
- Fox, G. A., & Sabbagh, G. J. (2009). Comment on “major factors influencing the efficacy of vegetated buffers on sediment trapping: A review and analysis,” by xingmei Liu, xuyang zhang, and minghua zhang in the journal of environmental quality 2008 37:1667–1674. *Journal of Environmental Quality*, 38(1), 1–3. <https://doi.org/10.2134/jeq2009.00011e>
- Francia Martínez, J. R., Durán Zuazo, V. H., & Martínez Raya, A. (2006). Environmental impact from mountainous olive orchards under different soil-management systems (SE Spain). *Science of the Total Environment*, 358(1–3), 46–60. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2005.05.036>
- García-Estringana, P., Alonso-Blázquez, N., Marques, M. J., Bienes, R., González-Andrés, F., & Alegre, J. (2013). Use of Mediterranean legume shrubs to control soil erosion and runoff in central Spain. A large-plot assessment under natural rainfall conducted during the stages of shrub establishment and subsequent colonisation. *Catena*, 102, 3–12. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.catena.2011.09.003>
- Gene, S. M., Hoekstra, P. F., Hannam, C., White, M., Truman, C., Hanson, M. L., et al. (2019). The role of vegetated buffers in agriculture and their regulation across Canada and the United States. *Journal of Environmental Management*, 243, 12–21. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2019.05.003>
- Gilley, J. E., Eghball, B., Kramer, L. A., & Moorman, T. B. (2000). Narrow grass hedge effects on runoff and soil loss. *Journal of Soil and Water Conservation*, 55(2), 190–196. <https://digitalcommons.unl.edu/biosysengfacpub/129>
- Gómez, J. A. (2017). Sustainability using cover crops in mediterranean tree crops, olives and vines – challenges and current knowledge. *Hungarian Geographical Bulletin*, 66(1), 13–28. <https://doi.org/10.15201/hungeobull.66.1.2>
- Gómez, J. A., & Soriano, M. A. (2020). Evaluation of the suitability of three autochthonous herbaceous species as cover crops under Mediterranean conditions through the calibration and validation of a temperature-based phenology model. *Agriculture, Ecosystems & Environment*, 291, 106788. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agee.2019.106788>
- Gumiere, S. J., Le Bissonnais, Y., Raclot, D., & Cheviron, B. (2011). Vegetated filter effects on sedimentological connectivity of agricultural catchments in erosion modelling: A review. *Earth Surface Processes and Landforms*, 36(1), 3–19. <https://doi.org/10.1002/esp.2042>
- Guzmán, G., Cabezas, J. M., Sánchez-Cuesta, R., Lora, Bauer, T., Strauss, P., et al. (2019). A field evaluation of the impact of temporary cover crops on soil properties and vegetation communities in southern Spain vineyards. *Agriculture, Ecosystems & Environment*, 272, 135–145. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agee.2018.11.010>
- Haddaway, N. R., Brown, C., Eales, J., Eggers, S., Josefsson, J., Kronvang, B., et al. (2018). The multifunctional roles of vegetated strips around and within agricultural fields. *Environmental Evidence*, 7(1), 1–43. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13750-018-0126-2>. BioMed Central Ltd.
- Hall, J. K., Hartwig, N. L., & Hoffman, L. D. (1983). Application mode and alternate cropping effects on atrazine losses from a hillside. *Journal of Environmental Quality*, 12(3), 336–340. <https://doi.org/10.2134/jeq1983.00472425001200030008x>
- Hall, R. M., Penke, N., Kriechbaum, M., Kratschmer, S., Jung, V., Chollet, S., et al. (2020). Vegetation management intensity and landscape diversity alter plant species richness, functional traits and community composition across European vineyards. *Agricultural Systems*, 177, Article 102706. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agsy.2019.102706>
- Hay, V., Pittroff, W., Tooman, E. E., & Meyer, D. (2006). Effectiveness of vegetative filter strips in attenuating nutrient and sediment runoff from irrigated pastures. *Journal of Agricultural Science*, 144(4), 349–360. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0021859606062616>
- Heckmann, T., Cavalli, M., Cerdan, O., Foerster, S., Javaux, M., Lode, E., et al. (2018). Indices of sediment connectivity: Opportunities, challenges and limitations. *Earth-Science Reviews*, 187, 77–108. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.earscirev.2018.08.004>
- Helmers, M. J., Eisenhauer, D. E., Dosskey, M. G., Franti, T. G., Brothers, J. M., & McCullough, M. C. (2005). Flow pathways and sediment trapping in a field-scale vegetative filter. *Transactions of the ASAE*, 48(3), 955–968. <https://doi.org/10.13031/2013.18508>
- Hoffmann, C. C., Kjaergaard, C., Uusi-Kämpä, J., Hansen, H. C. B., & Kronvang, B. (2009). Phosphorus retention in riparian buffers: Review of their efficiency. *Journal of Environmental Quality*, 38(5), 1942–1955. <https://doi.org/10.2134/jeq2008.0087>
- Hudek, C., Sterk, G., van Beek, R. L. P. H., & de Jong, S. M. (2014). Modelling soil erosion reduction by mahonia aquifolium on hillslopes in Hungary: The impact of soil stabilization by roots. *Catena*, 122, 159–169. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.catena.2014.06.017>
- Kiepe, P. (1996). Cover and barrier effect of Cassia siamea hedgerows on soil conservation in semi-arid Kenya. *Soil Technology*, 9(3), 161–171. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0933-3630\(96\)00010-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0933-3630(96)00010-4)
- Kleinman, P. J. A., Sharpley, A. N., Buda, A. R., McDowell, R. W., & Allen, A. L. (2011). Soil controls of phosphorus in runoff: Management barriers and opportunities. *Canadian Journal of Soil Science*, 91(3), 329–338. <https://doi.org/10.4141/cjss09106>
- Langbein, W. B., & Schumm, S. A. (1958). Yield of sediment in relation to mean annual precipitation. *Eos, Transactions American Geophysical Union*, 39(6), 1076–1084. <https://doi.org/10.1029/TR039i006p01076>
- Liu, Y., Engel, B. A., Flanagan, D. C., Gitau, M. W., McMillan, S. K., & Chaubey, I. (2017). A review on effectiveness of best management practices in improving hydrology and water quality: Needs and opportunities. *Science of the Total Environment*, 601–602, 580–593. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2017.05.212>
- Liu, Z. Y., Wang, G. L., Cao, P., & Yao, G. Z. (2012). Impact of different contour hedgerows on control of nutrient, soil and water loss on slope land in Danjiangkou Reservoir Region. In *Proceedings - 2012 international conference on computer distributed control and intelligent environmental monitoring* (pp. 364–368). CDCEM. <https://doi.org/10.1109/CDCEM.2012.93>, 2012.
- Liu, X., Zhang, X., & Zhang, M. (2008). Major factors influencing the efficacy of vegetated buffers on sediment trapping: A review and analysis. *Journal of Environmental Quality*, 37(5), 1667–1674. <https://doi.org/10.2134/jeq2007.0437>
- Mahoney, D. T., Fox, J. F., & Al Aamery, N. (2018). Watershed erosion modeling using the probability of sediment connectivity in a gently rolling system. *Journal of Hydrology*, 561, 862–883. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhydrol.2018.04.034>
- Martínez Raya, A., Durán Zuazo, V. H., & Francia Martínez, J. R. (2006). Soil erosion and runoff response to plant-cover strips on semiarid slopes (SE Spain). *Land Degradation & Development*, 17(1), 1–11. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ldr.674>
- McKergow, L. A., Weaver, D. M., Prosser, I. P., Grayson, R. B., & Reed, A. E. G. (2003). Before and after riparian management: Sediment and nutrient exports from a small agricultural catchment, Western Australia. *Journal of Hydrology*, 270(3–4), 253–272. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0022-1694\(02\)00286-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0022-1694(02)00286-X)
- Merritt, W. S., Letcher, R. A., & Jakeman, A. J. (2003). A review of erosion and sediment transport models. *Environmental Modelling & Software*, 18(8–9), 761–799. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1364-8152\(03\)00078-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1364-8152(03)00078-1)
- Mora, J., Gómez, J. A., Lora, A., Muñoz, F. J., & Rojo, M. (2019). Los elementos del paisaje agrario de la campiña de Córdoba: Una herramienta de interés social para la gestión de los recursos ambientales del territorio. <http://hdl.handle.net/10261/215849>
- Muñoz-Carpena, R., Parsons, J. E., & Gilliam, J. W. (1999). Modeling hydrology and sediment transport in vegetative filter strips. *Journal of Hydrology*, 214(1–4), 111–129. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0022-1694\(98\)00272-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0022-1694(98)00272-8)
- Nearing, M. A., Govers, G., & Norton, L. D. (1999). Variability in soil erosion data from replicated plots. *Soil Science Society of America Journal*, 63(6), 1829–1835.

- <https://doi.org/10.2136/sssaj1999.6361829x>
- Nilsson, L., Clough, Y., Smith, H. G., Alkan Olsson, J., Brady, M. V., Hristov, J., et al. (2019). A suboptimal array of options erodes the value of CAP ecological focus areas. *Land Use Policy*, 85, 407–418. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landusepol.2019.04.005>
- NRCS. (2010). Conservation practice standard - vegetative barrier. Code, 601.
- Patty, L., Real, B., & Gril, J. J. (1997). The use of grassed buffer strips to remove pesticides, nitrate and soluble phosphorus compounds from runoff water. *Pesticide Science*, 49(3), 243–251. [https://doi.org/10.1002/\(SICI\)1096-9063\(199703\)49:3<243::AID-PS510>3.0.CO;2-8](https://doi.org/10.1002/(SICI)1096-9063(199703)49:3<243::AID-PS510>3.0.CO;2-8)
- Pätzold, S., Klein, C., & Brümmer, G. W. (2007). Run-off transport of herbicides during natural and simulated rainfall and its reduction by vegetated filter strips. *Soil Use & Management*, 23(3), 294–305. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1475-2743.2007.00097.x>
- Peel, M. C., Finlayson, B. L., & McMahon, T. A. (2007). Updated world map of the Köppen-Geiger climate classification. *Hydrology and Earth System Sciences*, 11(5), 1633–1644. <https://doi.org/10.5194/hess-11-1633-2007>
- Pilon, C., Moore, P. A., Pote, D. H., Pennington, J. H., Martin, J. W., Brauer, D. K., et al. (2017). Long-term effects of grazing management and buffer strips on soil erosion from pastures. *Journal of Environmental Quality*, 46(2), 364–372. <https://doi.org/10.2134/jeq2016.09.0378>
- Ramler, D., Stutter, M., Weigelhofer, G., Quinton, J. N., Hood-Nowotny, R., & Strauss, P. (2022). Keeping up with phosphorus dynamics: Overdue conceptual changes in vegetative filter strip research and management. *Frontiers in Environmental Science*, 10, Article 764333. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fenvs.2022.764333>
- Rodríguez, O. S. P. (1997). Hedgerows and mulch as soil conservation measures evaluated under field simulated rainfall. *Soil Technology*, 11(1), 79–93. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0933-3630\(96\)00117-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0933-3630(96)00117-1)
- Rüttimann, M., Schaub, D., Prasuhn, V., & Rüegg, W. (1995). Measurement of runoff and soil erosion on regularly cultivated fields in Switzerland - some critical considerations. *Catena*, 25(1–4), 127–139. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0341-8162\(95\)00005-D](https://doi.org/10.1016/0341-8162(95)00005-D)
- Saco, P. M., & Moreno-De Las Heras, M. (2013). Ecogeomorphic coevolution of semiarid hillslopes: Emergence of banded and striped vegetation patterns through interaction of biotic and abiotic processes. *Water Resources Research*, 49(1), 115–126. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2012WR012001>
- Salah, A. M. A., Prasse, R., & Marschner, B. (2016). Intercropping with native perennial plants protects soil of arable fields in semi-arid lands. *Journal of Arid Environments*, 130, 1–13. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jaridenv.2016.02.015>
- Schmitt, T. J., Dosskey, M. G., & Hoagland, K. D. (1999). Filter strip performance and processes for different vegetation, widths, and contaminants. *Journal of Environmental Quality*, 28(5), 1479–1489. <https://doi.org/10.2134/jeq1999.00472425002800050013x>
- Schulte, L. A., Niemi, J., Helmers, M. J., Liebman, M., Arbuckle, J. G., James, D. E., et al. (2017). Prairie strips improve biodiversity and the delivery of multiple ecosystem services from corn–soybean croplands. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America*, 114(42), 11247–11252. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1620229114>
- Schultz, R.C., Isenhardt, T.M., Colleti, J.P., Simpkins, W.W., Udawatta, R.P., & Schultz, P.L. (2009). Riparian and upland buffer practices (A. S. of Agronomy (ed.); 2 nd). <https://doi.org/10.2134/2009.northamericanagroforestry.2ed.c8>
- Schütte, R., Plaas, E., Gómez, J. A., & Guzmán, G. (2020). Profitability of erosion control with cover crops in European vineyards under consideration of environmental costs. *Environmental Development*, 35, Article 100521. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envdev.2020.100521>
- Shiono, T., Yamamoto, N., Haraguchi, N., & Yoshinaga, A. (2007). Performance of grass strips for sediment control in Okinawa. *Japan Agricultural Research Quarterly*, 41(4), 291–297. <https://doi.org/10.6090/jarq.41.291>
- Soriano, M. A., Cabezas, J. M., & Gómez, J. A. (2023). Field Evaluation of Selected Autochthonous Herbaceous Species for Cover Crops in Mediterranean Woody Crops. *European Journal of Agronomy*, 143, 126723. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eja.2022.126723>
- Srivastava, A., Yetemen, O., Saco, P. M., Rodríguez, J. F., Kumari, N., & Chun, K. P. (2022). Influence of orographic precipitation on coevolving landforms and vegetation in semi-arid ecosystems. *Earth Surface Processes and Landforms*, 47(12), 2846–2862. <https://doi.org/10.1002/esp.5427>
- Tzivilakis, J., Warner, D. J., Green, A., & Lewis, K. A. (2019). Spatial analysis of the benefits and burdens of ecological focus areas for water-related ecosystem services vulnerable to climate change in Europe. *Mitigation and Adaptation Strategies for Global Change*, 24(2), 205–233. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s1027-018-9807-y>
- Unger, I. M., Goynne, K. W., Kremer, R. J., & Kennedy, A. C. (2013). Microbial community diversity in agroforestry and grass vegetative filter strips. *Agroforestry Systems*, 87(2), 395–402. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10457-012-9559-8>
- Uusi-Kämpä, J. (2005). Phosphorus purification in buffer zones in cold climates. *Ecological Engineering*, 24(5), 491–502. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoleng.2005.01.013>
- Uusi-Kämpä, J., & Jauhiainen, L. (2010). Long-term monitoring of buffer zone efficiency under different cultivation techniques in boreal conditions. *Agriculture, Ecosystems & Environment*, 137(1–2), 75–85. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agee.2010.01.002>
- Wanyama, J., Herremans, K., Maetens, W., Isabirye, M., Kahimba, F., Kimaro, D., et al. (2012). Effectiveness of tropical grass species as sediment filters in the riparian zone of Lake Victoria. *Soil Use & Management*, 28(3), 409–418. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1475-2743.2012.00409.x>
- Wendt, R. C., Alberts, E. E., & Hjelmfelt, A. T. (1986). Variability of runoff and soil loss from fallow experimental plots. *Soil Science Society of America Journal*, 50(3), 730–736. <https://doi.org/10.2136/sssaj1986.03615995005000030035x>
- Winter, S., Bauer, T., Strauss, P., Kratschmer, S., Paredes, D., Popescu, D., et al. (2018). Effects of vegetation management intensity on biodiversity and ecosystem services in vineyards: A meta-analysis. *Journal of Applied Ecology*, 55(5), 2484–2495. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1365-2664.13124>
- Wolka, K., Mulder, J., & Biazin, B. (2018). Effects of soil and water conservation techniques on crop yield, runoff and soil loss in sub-saharan africa: A review. *Agricultural Water Management*, 207, 67–79. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agwat.2018.05.016>
- Xiao, B., Wang, Q., Wang, hai, fang, H., Dai, Q. hou, & Wu, J. ying (2011). The effects of narrow grass hedges on soil and water loss on sloping lands with alfalfa (*Medicago sativa* L.) in Northern China. *Geoderma*, 167–168, 91–102. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geoderma.2011.09.010>
- Yang, F., Yang, Y., Li, H., & Cao, M. (2015). Removal efficiencies of vegetation-specific filter strips on nonpoint source pollutants. *Ecological Engineering*, 82, 145–158. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoleng.2015.04.018>
- Yuan, Y., Bingner, R. L., & Locke, M. A. (2009). A review of effectiveness of vegetative buffers on sediment trapping in agricultural areas. *Ecohydrology*, 2(3), 321–336. <https://doi.org/10.1002/eco.82>